

WHO
Strategic Advisory Group
on Malaria Eradication

Working papers

Group 1: Potential economic benefits of malaria elimination and eradication

Title

Projected impact of investing towards universal coverage of malaria control interventions on economic outputs

Authors

Seoni Han (The Graduate Institute, Switzerland)

Jean-Louis Arcand (The Graduate Institute, Switzerland)

Jeremy Lauer (WHO, Switzerland)

Edith Patouillard (WHO, Switzerland)

Contact

seoni.han@graduateinstitute.ch

This working paper was commissioned by the WHO Strategic Advisory Group on Malaria Eradication between 2016 and 2019.

The designations employed and the presentation of the material in this publication do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of the Secretariat of the World Health Organization concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries.

The mention of specific companies or of certain manufacturers' products does not imply that they are endorsed or recommended by the World Health Organization in preference to others of a similar nature that are not mentioned. Errors and omissions excepted, the names of proprietary products are distinguished by initial capital letters.

This report contains the collective views of the authors and does not necessarily represent the decisions or the stated policies of the World Health Organization or the Strategic Advisory Group on Malaria Eradication.

Projected Impact of Investing Towards Universal Coverage of Malaria Control Interventions On Economic Outputs

Seoni Han, Graduate Institute Geneva

Jean-Louis Arcand, Graduate Institute Geneva

Jeremy Lauer, WHO Department of Health Systems Governance and Financing

Edith Patouillard, WHO Global Malaria Programme

Abstract

We investigate the impact of increasing investments towards universal coverage of WHO-recommended malaria control interventions on economic outputs in high burden malaria endemic countries. Our analysis considers the channels through which greater investments in scaling-up coverage and associated burden reduction affect physical capital accumulation and labor supply, and what difference changes in these two production factors eventually make on gross domestic product (GDP) and per capita income. We use a human capital augmented Solow model to project changes in aggregated national and per capita income across 29 malaria-endemic countries accounting together for 95% of global malaria cases and deaths in 2016. Investing towards universal coverage of essential malaria control interventions would contribute to an annual gain in aggregated GDP of 0.16% over the period 2016-2030 compared to a counterfactual of sustained coverage at baseline levels. Most of these economic gains would come from averted malaria morbidity over the study period.

1. Introduction

The literature provides some evidence of correlation between malaria and economic growth. Gallup and Sachs using cross-country regression for the period 1965-1990 find that a 10% reduction in malaria is associated with 0.3% higher growth, *ceteris paribus* [1]. More recently, a study by Nayantara Sarma and colleagues estimate malaria eradication to be associated with a 5% increase in per-capita income, equivalent to an estimated gain of 0.15% of world GDP in 2015. The importance of malaria control also has been reaffirmed with microeconomic studies at household or firm level. Evidence shows that malaria imposes loss of labour productivity leading to substantial economic losses on households and firms [2-6]. The microeconomic studies, however, do not provide insights on the channels of how malaria affects production factors and in turn economic outputs. Our paper contributes to identify these channels and what difference changes in these channels eventually make on economic outputs. The next section of this paper describes the methodology and is followed by a presentation of results.

2. Methods

2.1 Analytical framework

The analysis was undertaken using WHO tool for Economic Projections of Illness and Cost (EPIC). The theoretical framework is described in Annex 1¹. Briefly, EPIC considers two channels through which improvements in the health status of a country can impact its national income, including physical capital and labour. EPIC uses the augmented Solow growth model with a Cobb-Douglas production function that relates the contribution of different factors to production levels in a country:

$$Y_t = \gamma * A * K_t^\alpha * (H * L_t)^{1-\alpha}$$

where Y is the national income, A the total factor productivity, K the physical capital, H the human capital, L the labour force, γ is a scaling factor, and $0 < \alpha < 1$, with α the elasticity of income to production factors.

¹ Annex 1 forms a separate document shared with other papers to be reviewed by the Scientific Advisory Group on malaria eradication in November 2018.

Investing in malaria control interventions contributes to reduce disease morbidity and associated mortality. A reduction in malaria morbidity can improve the productivity of the labour force by reducing the number of work days lost from malaria or days lost from caring for an infected child or relative². Associated savings in health care spending from averting malaria cases is hypothesized to increase capital accumulation. Malaria control and elimination interventions could, however, negatively affect capital accumulation as they require investments that could have been saved or otherwise put to an alternative use. Finally, a decline in mortality would increase the size of the labour force³.

2.2 Country selection

We selected 29 malaria-endemic countries that accounted for 95% of malaria cases and related deaths in 2016⁴. The selected countries include Nigeria, Democratic Republic of Congo, India, Mozambique, Ghana, Mali, Burkina Faso, Niger, Uganda, United Republic of Tanzania, Cameroon, Cote d Ivoire, Guinea, Rwanda, Malawi, Kenya, Angola, Benin, Zambia, Togo, Ethiopia, Sierra Leone, Chad, South Sudan, Burundi, Madagascar, Central African Republic, Papua New Guinea, and Pakistan. The aggregated income of these countries was US\$ 3,930,031 million in 2016 (min US\$ 1,899 million - max 2,360,088 million). Of the 29-selected malaria-endemic countries, 19 were categorized as low-income countries and 10 as lower middle-income countries⁵ in 2016.

2.3 Scenarios

In each country, we explore the impact of different investment levels in malaria control interventions and associated changes in coverage, malaria case incidence and mortality rates on economic outputs for the period 2016-2030. Economic outputs are expressed in terms of national and per capita income.

One scenario assumes a scale-up of intervention coverage from 2011-2013 levels to those described in Table 1 and is referred as the “Scale-up” scenario. A second scenario, the “Counterfactual” assumes

² It was assumed that a malaria case in an adult reduced adult productivity by 100% and that a malaria case in a child reduced adult productivity by 100% for U5 and 50% for 5-14 years of age. The model was also run using 60% for U5 and 30% for 5-14 years of age to assess the sensitivity of results to this assumption.

³A reduction in mortality rate is assumed to increase the supply of labor in future years.

⁴Burden estimates from World Malaria Report 2017.

⁵ According to the World bank classifications for year 2017.

<https://datahelpdesk.worldbank.org/knowledgebase/articles/906519-world-bank-country-and-lending-groups>, accessed 01 September 2018.

2011-2013 average levels of intervention coverage are sustained until 2030 (Table 1).

Net annual differences in national and per capita income between “Scale Up” and “Sustain” scenarios were calculated for each country. Results were then aggregated across the selected 29 malaria endemic countries.

Table 1: Modelled coverage levels, by intervention, under “Scale-up” and “Counterfactual” scenarios

Scenario	Intervention	Baseline	2020 coverage targets	2025 coverage targets	2030 coverage targets
“Sustain”	All	Maintain coverage of all interventions at 2011–2013 levels, assumed constant until 2015.			
“Scale-up”	Vector control, incl LLIN and IRS	Means of 2011–2013 country-specific coverage	80% with LLIN replaced every 3 years	90% with LLIN replaced every 2 years	Maintain coverage
	Other vector control measures	10% additional coverage with complementary control measures for resistance management			
	SMC	0%	80%	95%	Maintain
	IPTp	0%	80%	90%	Maintain
	Blood tests, using RDTs or microscopy	20%			90%
		10% G6PD testing			90%
Treatment of uncomplicated cases	2013 country-specific coverage	90% at public facilities, 50% in communities		75% community based treatment	
Treatment of severe cases	100% hospitalised cases treated with quinine	100% hospitalised cases treated with injectable artesunate	50% severe cases with rectal artesunate in communities	75% severe cases with rectal artesunate in communities	

2.4 Data sources

Economic data on capital depreciation rate and human capital index are taken from the Penn World Table 9.0. Depreciation rates are calculated as the average of the rates over the 10-year period between 2005 and 2014. Human capital index per person of Penn World Table 9.0 is based on years of schooling [7] and returns to education [8]. In the model, human capital for each country is the human capital index of year 2014.

GDP data are obtained from WHO for the period of 2016-2030. GDP per capita for the Sustain scenario is calculated as GDP divided by the population at risk while that for the Scale-up scenario as GDP divided by newly estimated population with the demographic changes taken account of from averted mortality of adults and children.

The saving rate is the gross domestic savings as percentage of GDP from the World Bank Development Index database. Saving rates are the average of the observed figures over the 10-year period between 2005 and 2014. The country-specific elasticity of income to physical capital, and total factor productivity and its growth, are estimated based on the data from Penn World Table 9.0.

Labor force data are calculated by multiplying the population with the labor force participation rate for the relevant age groups. The labor force participation rates by sex and age groups for countries are from the ILO online database⁶. The scaling factor is chosen to benchmark the GDP of the initial year and is equally applied to the rest of the period.

The total amount of investments needed to increase coverage to the targets described in Table 1 was estimated following the methodology described in [9]. Under the Counterfactual Scenario, total resource needs were estimated to increase from 2,698 million in 2016 (< 1% of aggregated GDP) to 3677 million in 2030; and, under the Scale-up Scenario from 2,999 million to 7,143 million respectively.

The effect of the different amount of investments and associated coverage levels on malaria case incidence and deaths was estimated using a dynamic mathematical model of malaria transmission [10].

Scaling-up interventions to the targets described in Table 1 could lead to a decline of 58% in malaria

⁶https://www.ilo.org/ilostat/faces/wcnav_defaultSelection?_afzLoop=3110499814673610&_afzWindowMode=0&_afzWindowId=null#!%40%40%3F_afzWindowId%3Dnull%26_afzLoop%3D3110499814673610%26_afzWindowMode%3D0%26_adf.ctrl-state%3Dkja3x108r_4, accessed 18 August 2016

case incidence and 71% in death rates over the study period (Figure 1). Under the Counterfactual scenario, sustaining intervention coverage at baseline levels would imply increasing malaria case incidence and sustaining death rates during the study period (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Predicted malaria incidence per person per year for the period 2016-2030 across 29 countries

Figure 2: Predicted deaths per 1000 people per year for the period 2016-2030 across 29 countries

3. Results

Investing in significant scale-up of malaria control intervention coverage could contribute to a 0.16% gain (US\$ 264,779 million) in aggregated GDP over the period 2016-2030. Gains are expected to increase over the study period, with GDP gains of 0.09% in 2020, 0.17% in 2025 and 0.23% in 2030 (Table 2).

Similar results were found in terms of aggregated per capita income, with average gain of 0.14% (US\$ 2,094) during the period 2016-2030, with gains of 0.08% in 2020, 0.15% in 2025 and 0.20% in 2030 (Table 3).

Reductions in malaria case incidence and mortality would contribute for 77% and 23% of the total gains in GDP, respectively (Figures 3 and 4).

Table 2: Aggregated GDP (million US\$) by scenario and net change between scenarios (million US\$, %)

Scenario/Year	2016	2020	2025	2030	Cumulative 2016-2030
Sustain (US\$)	3,930,030	6,997,133	12,503,540	20,189,698	162,280,854
Scale-up (US\$)	3,930,030	7,003,508	12,524,868	20,236,219	162,545,634
Gain/Loss (US\$)	0	6,374	21,328	46,521	264,779
%Gain/Loss	0.00%	0.09%	0.17%	0.23%	0.16%

Table 3: Aggregated per capita income (US\$) by scenario and net change between scenarios (US\$, %)

Scenario/Year	2016	2020	2025	2030	Cumulative 2016-2030
Sustain (US\$)	49,300	74,688	115,570	168,986	1,531,775
Scale-up (US\$)	49,297	74,747	115,745	169,327	1,533,869
Gain/Loss (US\$)	-3.17	58.59	174.82	341.60	2,094
%Gain/Loss	-0.01%	0.08%	0.15%	0.20%	0.14%

Figure 3: Contributions of morbidity and mortality declines to gains in GDP.

Figure 4: Contributions of morbidity and mortality declines to gains in GDP in 2020, 2025 and 2030

References:

1. Gallup, J.L. and Sachs, J.D., 2001. The economic burden of malaria. *The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene*, 64(1_suppl), pp.85-96.
2. Ettlting M, McFarland DA, Schultz LJ, *et al.* Economic impact of malaria in Malawian households. *Tropical medicine and parasitology: official organ of Deutsche Tropenmedizinische Gesellschaft and of Deutsche Gesellschaft für Technische Zusammenarbeit (GTZ)*. 1994;45(1):74-9.
3. Guiguemde TR, Dao F, Curtis V, *et al.* Household expenditure on malaria prevention and treatment for families in the town of Bobo-Dioulasso, Burkina Faso. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. 1994;88(3):285-7.
4. Attanayake N, Fox-Rushby J, Mills A. Household costs of 'malaria' morbidity: a study in Matale district, Sri Lanka. *Tropical Medicine & International Health*. 2000;5(9):595-606.
5. Ayieko P, Akumu AO, Griffiths UK, *et al.* The economic burden of inpatient paediatric care in Kenya: household and provider costs for treatment of pneumonia, malaria and meningitis. *Cost Effectiveness and Resource Allocation*. 2009;7(1):3.
6. Bleakley H. Malaria eradication in the Americas: A retrospective analysis of childhood exposure. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*. 2010;2(2):1-45.
7. Barro, R and Lee, JW. A new data set of educational attainment in the world, 1950-20310. *Journal of Development Economics*. 2013, 104: 184-198
8. Psacharopoulos G. Returns to investment in education: A global update. *World development*. 1994;22(9):1325-43.
9. Patouillard E, Griffin J, Bhatt S, *et al.* Global investment targets for malaria control and elimination between 2016 and 2030. *BMJ global health*. 2017;2(2):e000176.
10. Griffin JT, Bhatt S, Sinka ME, *et al.* Potential for reduction of burden and local elimination of malaria by reducing Plasmodium falciparum malaria transmission: a mathematical modelling study. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*. 2016;16(4):465-72.